

Phenolic compounds from *Celastrus angulatus*

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Four phenolic compounds (+)-catechin (1), (-)-epicatechin (2), 2,4,6-trimethoxyphenol-1-*O*- β -D-glucopyranoside (3), 3 β ,7,3'-trihydroxy-4'-methoxyflavan-5-*O*- β -D-glucopyranoside (4) together with dulcitol (5) have been isolated from the ethanol extracts of the root bark of *Celastrus angulatus*. Among them, compound 4 is a new methyl derivative of flavan-3-olglycoside. Compound 3 is first isolated as a new natural product.

Celastrus angulatus Max. (Celastraceae), widely distributed in China, has long been used as a traditional natural insecticide and a folk medicine for the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis and bacterial infection. The extract of its root bark exhibited antifeedant, narcotic and insecticidal activities on several insect species¹. The anti-inflammatory, anti-HIV and antitumor activities about this plant have also been reported². Various dihydro- β -agarofuran sesquiterpene derivatives have been isolated from the lipophilic extracts of the root bark, seeds and leaves of the Celastraceae family. Some of them showed various biological activities³. But little phytochemical attention has been paid to the aqueous extracts of plants belonging to the family. Our study on the water-soluble fraction of the ethanol extracts of the root bark of *C. angulatus* led to the isolation of four phenolic compound : (+)-catechin (1), (-)-epicatechin (2), 2,4,6-trimethoxyphenol-1-*O*- β -D-glucopyranoside (3), 3 β ,7,3'-trihydroxy-4'-methoxyflavan-5-*O*- β -D-glucopyranoside (4), together with dulcitol (5). Among them, compound 4 is a new

methyl derivative of flavan-3-olglycoside. These kinds of compounds were rarely found in nature, whereas many flavan-4-ones substituted with methoxyl groups have been isolated from a variety of plants, although these two types of compounds are assumed to be biosynthetically related to each other. Compound 3 is first isolated as a new natural product. Compounds 1, 2 and 5 were identified respectively as (+)-catechin, (-)-epicatechin and dulcitol by comparison their physical and spectrum data with those reported⁴.

Experimental

M.p.s are uncorrected. IR spectra were measured on a Nicolet FT-IR 10DX spectrophotometer, ¹³C and ¹H NMR spectra on a Bruker AM-400 spectrometer and FAB-MS, EIMS spectra on a VG Autospec 3000 spectrometer. Silica gel (160–200 mesh and 10–40 μ m, Ocean Chemical Plant of Qingdao), Sephadex LH-20, Polymide, macroporous adsorption resin (D₁₀₁) were used in column chromatography. TLC was conducted on precoated silica gel GF₂₅₄ plate (0.2 mm, Ocean chemical Plant of Qingdao). Spots were detected by spraying with 5% H₂SO₄ of 5% FeCl₃ alcohol solution followed by heating.

The root barks of *C. angulatus* Max. were collected from Lu Shan (Henan Province of China) in the autumn of 1994, and identified by Professor Zhan Guoliang (Lan Zhou University).

The dry powdered root bark of the *C. angulatus* were extracted with alcohol four times (each for 3h) under reflux. The ethanol extracts were dispersed in water, and then extracted successively with petroleum ether, chloroform and ether. The aqueous layer was concentrated under vacuum at the temperature below 50° to remove the organic solvent.

Fig. 1. NOESY of compound 4.

The concentrated water solution was then subjected to chromatography on macroporous absorption resin D₁₀₁, eluting with water first and then methanol. Methanol was removed under vacuum to give the aqueous extract (120 g) which was chromatographed repeatedly on silica gel (with CHCl₃-MeOH-H₂O in various proportion as eluent), Sephadex LH-20 (with H₂O containing increasing amounts of methanol from 1 : 0 to 0 : 1 as eluent) and polyamide column (with H₂O containing increasing amounts of methanol as eluent) and led to the isolation of compounds 1-5.

Compound 3 : Colorless needles, m.p. 209~210°; FAB⁺ MS (*m/z*, %) : 347(M+1, 100), 184(M-162, 53); ¹³C DEPT spectrum, a molecular formula C₁₅H₂₂O₉; ¹H NMR (CD₃OD) δ 6.48 (ppm) (two aromatic protons), 2.68 (3H) and 3.80 (6H) (three methoxyl groups), anomeric proton signal at δ 4.80 (d, *J* 7.3 Hz) indicated that the sugar moiety is linked to the aglycone in β-form; ¹³C NMR (CD₃OD) δ 158.01 (C-1), 154.83 (C-2, C-6), 96.35 (C-3, C-5), 156.03 (C-4), 56.61 (C-2, C-6-OCH₃), 61.22 (C-4-OCH₃), 103.25 (C-g₁), 74.98 (C-g₂), 78.14 (C-g₃), 71.73 (C-g₄), 78.44 (C-g₅), 62.76 (C-g₆). Hence compound 3 was determined to be 2,4,6-trimethoxyphenol-1-*O*-β-D-glucopyranoside.

This compound was isolated by Nonaka *et al.*⁵ as a hydrolysate of a new natural product 1-*O*-β-D-(6'-*O*-galloyl)glucopyranoside from the bark of *Quercus stenophylla* Makino. We first isolated compound 3 as a new natural product and hence report its ¹³C NMR data.

Compound 4 : White powder from MeOH, m.p. >200°; FAB⁻ mass spectrum, molecular formula weight 466, ¹³C DEPT spectrum, molecular formula C₂₂H₂₆O₁₁; ν_{max} 3416 (OH), 2927, 1607, 1518 cm⁻¹ (benzene skeleton); ¹H NMR (C₅D₅N) δ 3.27 (1H, dd, *J* 16.3, 8.4 Hz, H-4β), 3.55 (1H, dd, *J* 16.4, 5.4 Hz, H-4α), 3.69 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.96 (2H, m, H-g₆), 4.33 (1H, m, H-3), 4.48 (1H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz, anomeric-H), 5.08 (1H, d, *J* 2.2 Hz, H-6), 5.48 (1H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz, H-2), 6.72 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz, H-8), 6.90 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, H-5' and H-6'), 7.00 (1H, s, H-2'); ¹³C NMR (C₅D₅N) δ 82.96 (C-2), 67.66 (C-3), 29.51 (C-4), 156.66 (C-5), 97.08 (C-6), 158.61 (C-7), 98.04 (C-8), 158.00 (C-9), 103.01 (C-10), 133.82 (C-1'), 116.00 (C-2'), 148.47 (C-3'), 148.49 (C-4'), 119.13 (C-5'), 112.41 (C-6'), 102.49 (C-g₁), 75.01 (C-g₂), 78.71 (C-g₃), 71.19 (C-g₄), 78.70 (C-g₅), 62.34 (C-g₆), 56.06 (OCH₃).

The ¹H and ¹³C NMR, especially the H-2 signal in ¹H NMR and the C-2, C-3 chemical shifts in ¹³C NMR were

very similar to those of compound 1. We can suppose that there is a flavan-3-ol moiety in compound 4. The ¹³C signals existing at 62.34–78.70 and 102.49 ppm showed that there probably a glucose moiety is present. The *m/z* 304 (M⁺-162) in FABMS further supports the presence of glucose moiety. The ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra also indicated that the compound has a methoxy group (δ_H 3.69 ppm, 3H, s; δ_C 56.06 ppm). Finally, the structure of compound 4 was determined by 2D-NMR (Fig. 1).

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